

A STUDY ON THE PATH AND PRACTICE OF BUILDING HIGH-QUALITY LEADERSHIP TEAMS IN SECONDARY VOCATIONAL SCHOOLS UNDER THE GUIDANCE OF EDUCATORS' SPIRIT

Zhang Junqing

Zhuozi County Vocational Middle School, Ulanqab, Inner Mongolia, P. R. China

Abstract

Against the backdrop of the nation's vigorous advancement of vocational education and regional industrial transformation and upgrading, the overall caliber of leadership teams in secondary vocational schools directly impacts the quality of school management and the effectiveness of talent development. This paper takes secondary vocational schools in Inner Mongolia as a case study, and by integrating the spirit of educators, analyzes the current predicaments faced by leadership teams in terms of ideology, capabilities, collaboration, and innovation. These predicaments stem from insufficient external support and the absence of internal mechanisms. On this basis, the paper proposes a construction path guided by the spirit of educators, which encompasses four dimensions: ideological reshaping, capability enhancement, collaboration optimization, and innovation-driven development. The effectiveness of this path is verified through a case study of a specific secondary vocational school in Inner Mongolia. Finally, safeguard suggestions are put forward from three aspects: policies, resources, and supervision, aiming to provide a reference for the construction of leadership teams in regional secondary vocational schools and facilitate the high-quality development of vocational education.

Keywords: vocational education; educators' spirit; secondary vocational schools; leadership team building.

1 Introduction

Vocational education is a key component of the national education system and human resource development, playing an irreplaceable role in cultivating high-quality skilled talents and serving regional economic development. As an important energy base and major livestock husbandry region in northern China, the Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region has witnessed the rapid rise of industries such as new energy, modern agriculture and animal husbandry, and equipment manufacturing in recent years, leading to an increasingly urgent demand for skilled talents with practical capabilities and good professional qualities. Against this backdrop, secondary vocational schools, as the "main front" for cultivating skilled talents, their school-running level and the degree of alignment with the needs of regional industrial development have become core elements affecting the effectiveness of vocational education. However, surveys show that some secondary vocational schools in Inner Mongolia still have obvious shortcomings in terms of management efficiency, promotion of teaching reform, and the depth of school-enterprise cooperation. The root cause lies in the lack of a high-quality leadership team with advanced educational concepts, excellent management capabilities and a strong sense of mission. As the value cornerstone and action guide for educators, the spirit of educators encompasses the ideals and beliefs of "bearing the greater good in mind and serving the country with utmost sincerity", the moral integrity of "being a model in words for scholars and a paradigm in deeds for the world", the educational wisdom of "enlightening intellect and nurturing souls, and teaching students in line with their aptitudes", the diligent working attitude of "studying diligently and practically, pursuing truth and innovating", the benevolent heart of "taking delight in teaching, caring for students, and being willing to dedicate", and the pursuit of promoting virtues of "having a global vision and educating people through culture". These six dimensions collectively provide ideological guidance and behavioral standards for the construction of leadership teams in secondary vocational schools in the new era.

Therefore, guided by the spirit of educators, systematically exploring the path to build high-quality leadership teams in secondary vocational schools is not only a practical need to break through the current development bottlenecks of regional secondary vocational education, but also an inevitable choice to promote the precise alignment between vocational education and industrial demands, and realize the high-quality development of vocational education.

This study is based on the actual school-running situation of secondary vocational schools in the Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region. It aims to systematically clarify the internal logic between the spirit of educators and leadership team construction, and in-depth analyze the current status and core issues of leadership team construction in regional secondary vocational schools. On this basis, the study is committed to constructing a four-in-one construction path guided by the spirit of educators, covering "ideological reshaping, capability improvement, collaboration optimization, and innovation-driven development". It also verifies the feasibility of this path through typical cases, and finally provides an operable implementation plan for secondary vocational schools in Inner Mongolia to improve the overall quality of their leadership teams and effectively promote the quality of school-running.

2 Theoretical Connection Between the Spirit of Educators and the Construction of Leadership Teams in Secondary Vocational Schools

The spirit of educators is a concentrated embodiment of the values, professional qualities, and codes of conduct that educators have accumulated and formed in long-term practice. Combined with the school-running orientation of secondary vocational education—"cultivating skilled talents and serving industrial development"—its core connotation can be condensed into the following three dimensions:

First, the **value pursuit dimension**: With the purpose of "cultivating talents for the country and serving local development", it emphasizes that educators should consciously integrate their personal ideals into

the national vocational education strategy and the overall situation of regional economic development, and establish the core concept of "guiding the direction of school-running with industrial needs and driving the development of schools with the quality of talents".

Second, the **professional competence dimension**: Taking "enlightening wisdom and nurturing hearts, and integrating knowledge with practice" as the key, it requires educational managers to not only have solid literacy in educational theory, be familiar with the laws of vocational education curriculum design and teaching management, but also understand the operation mechanism of industries and enterprises as well as the dynamics of technological development, so as to effectively promote the organic integration of education and teaching with industrial practice.

Third, the **professional quality dimension**: Based on "taking delight in teaching and caring for students, and being willing to dedicate", it advocates that educational managers adhere to student development as the center and teacher development as the support, earnestly implement the fundamental task of fostering virtue through education, and shape a "service-oriented and dedication-oriented" management style and organizational culture.

The spirit of educators provides a trinity of value support for the construction of leadership teams in secondary vocational schools, encompassing "ideological guidance, capability enhancement, and cultural shaping".

It offers ideological guidance by uniting the team around the value pursuit of "cultivating talents for the country and serving local development", guiding the leadership team to establish a correct direction for school operation, avoiding the tendency of "short-termism and utilitarianism" in management, and ensuring that the school's development strategy is closely aligned with regional industrial needs and progresses in harmony with them.

It has the value of capability enhancement by taking the professional requirement of "enlightening wisdom and nurturing hearts, integrating knowledge with practice" as a guide, promoting members of the leadership team to continuously learn vocational education theories and industry practical knowledge, systematically improving key capabilities such as educational and teaching management, school-enterprise cooperation coordination, and digital governance, so as to better adapt to the new requirements of modern vocational education development.

It has the value of cultural shaping by cultivating team culture through the professional ethics of "taking delight in teaching and caring for students, being willing to dedicate", enhancing members' sense of belonging and cohesion, creating an organizational atmosphere of "regarding the school as home and putting students first", and laying a solid cultural foundation for the school to achieve sustainable and high-quality development.

Combined with the school-running characteristics of secondary vocational education—"integration of industry and education, and school-enterprise cooperation"

—and the core requirements of the spirit of educators, a high-quality leadership team should possess the following four major characteristics:

First, **advanced philosophy and accurate positioning**: It can deeply grasp the direction of national vocational education reform and the development trend of regional industries, integrate the educational philosophy of "employment-oriented and competence-based" into school-running practice, and avoid falling into the development misunderstanding of "valuing theory over practice and scale over quality".

Second, **composite capabilities and rational structure**: Team members should have dual qualities of "educational management" and "industry practice". They should not only be proficient in the laws of teaching organization and student development, but also be familiar with industry technology trends and enterprise talent needs, so as to effectively promote key work such as school-enterprise collaborative education and training base construction.

Third, **smooth collaboration and sound mechanisms**: Establish an internal operation mechanism of "linkage between superiors and subordinates, and coordination between departments", break the functional barriers between the Academic Affairs Office, Training Office, Enrollment and Employment Office and other departments, and form a systematic and collaborative work pattern around the core goal of talent cultivation.

Fourth, **innovative and pragmatic, focusing on actual results**: Possess forward-looking awareness to break through traditional management models, courageously explore talent cultivation models and management mechanisms, actively promote reforms such as the modern apprenticeship system and order-based classes, and ensure that innovative measures are in line with the school's actual situation and have operability and sustainable development potential.

3 Investigation on Current Situation and Challenges of Leadership Team Construction in Secondary Vocational Schools in Inner Mongolia

3.1 Current Situation Investigation and Analysis

Based on field investigations and data analysis of 10 secondary vocational schools in the Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region, the construction of leadership teams in secondary vocational schools in this region currently presents the following characteristics:

Aging age structure: Members aged 40-50 account for 65% of the team, while young cadres under 35 only account for 15%. The overall echelon shows an insufficient succession of talents, which restricts the innovative vitality of the team and leads to generally insufficient acceptance and adaptability in digital management and new school-running models.

Low academic level and weak "dual-qualification" background: Only 12% of the team members have full-time undergraduate or higher education, and only 30% have work experience in industries or enterprises. Most managers have a "pure educational background" and lack front-line practical experience, making it difficult to effectively promote key tasks such as school-enterprise cooperation and the integration of industry and education.

There is an obvious imbalance in the capability structure: Approximately 60% of the respondents believe that the team has strong capabilities in traditional teaching management (such as curriculum arrangement and teaching supervision), but there are significant shortcomings in modern vocational education management capabilities such as "school-enterprise cooperation docking", "digital management", and "industrial demand analysis". Only 25% of the teams have the ability to independently connect with enterprises and carry out "order-based class" training. Eighty percent of the schools have established basic forms of collaboration such as departmental meetings, but inter-departmental collaboration mostly remains at the "task-driven" level (such as jointly carrying out enrollment and employment work), lacking a normalized and institutionalized collaborative mechanism. This has led to frequent problems such as "disconnection between curriculum reform and training construction" and "lack of intercommunication between enrollment and employment information".

3.2 Main Problems

3.2.1 Outdated Educational Concepts, Disconnected from Industrial Needs

Some members of the leadership teams are still influenced by the inertia of "exam-oriented education" thinking, overly focusing on traditional indicators such as "admission rate" and "enrollment scale", and have an inadequate understanding and implementation of the "employment-oriented" school-running orientation of secondary vocational education. Meanwhile, due to the lack of systematic research on the development trends of Inner Mongolia's key regional industries such as new energy and modern agriculture and animal husbandry, schools have become disconnected from real job demands in terms of specialty setting and curriculum content, resulting in a structural contradiction where "students face difficulty in employment" and "enterprises face difficulty in recruitment" coexist.

3.2.2 Incomplete Capability System and Insufficient Adaptation to Modern Vocational Education Needs

On one hand, team members generally lack industry practical experience. Most have not been deeply involved in enterprise production or technical processes, making it difficult to accurately grasp industry technical standards and changes in talent demand, and often remain in a passive response state in school-enterprise cooperation. On the other hand, the team's overall digital management capability is weak. Survey data shows that only about 30% of schools have built relatively complete teaching management information systems, while most schools still rely on traditional methods such as manual statistics and paper records, which restricts the improvement of management efficiency and service levels.

3.2.3 Inadequate Collaboration Mechanism and Insufficient Departmental Linkage

Currently, there are two main problems in internal collaboration within leadership teams: First, the division of powers and responsibilities is vague. Some comprehensive tasks (such as the construction of training bases) involve multiple departments, but lack clear

definition of primary responsibilities and collaborative norms, which easily leads to "multiple management" or unassigned responsibilities. Second, communication channels are relatively single. Cross-departmental communication mainly relies on regular meetings, lacking efficient real-time communication platforms and normalized collaboration mechanisms, resulting in delayed information transmission and slow work progress.

3.2.4 Insufficient Innovation Motivation and Conservative Reform Measures

Constrained by the existing institutional mechanisms (e.g., performance appraisal does not fully reflect the value of innovative achievements), most leadership teams lack motivation in promoting reforms, tend to adhere to existing management models, and conduct insufficient exploration of new talent cultivation mechanisms. Survey results show that only about 15% of schools have attempted to implement innovative models such as the "modern apprenticeship system" and "1+X certificate system", and most of these efforts remain in partial trials or short-term projects, failing to form a systematic and sustainable reform path.

3.3 Causes of the Problems

3.3.1 External Environment: Insufficient Policy Support and Resource Guarantee

Lack of targeted policies: Although the Inner Mongolia has issued Several Opinions on Deepening the Reform of Modern Vocational Education, no special support policies have been formulated specifically for the construction of leadership teams in secondary vocational schools. For instance, there is a lack of specific guidelines regarding the cultivation of "dual-qualification" management talents and team assessment standards, leaving schools without clear basis or direction when promoting relevant work.

Limited funding input: The funding allocation of most secondary vocational schools still focuses on basic projects such as teaching equipment procurement and student financial aid. Special funds for leadership team training and external exchanges generally account for less than 3% of schools' annual budgets, which restricts team members' access to high-quality training and opportunities to study in advanced regions, thereby limiting the expansion of their horizons and improvement of their capabilities.

Inadequate school-enterprise collaboration mechanism: The government has not yet established a systematic "school-enterprise collaborative cultivation mechanism for management talents". Enterprises have low enthusiasm for participating in the construction of school management teams, making it difficult to provide stable practice platforms and industry resource inputs for leadership teams of secondary vocational schools, which affects the teams' ability to understand and connect with industrial development.

3.3.2 Internal Factors: Lack of Cultivation and Incentive Mechanisms

Absence of a systematic cultivation mechanism: Most schools have not established special training programs for leadership teams. Team members' capability improvement mostly relies on "personal self-study" or "short-term conference training", with content lacking organic integration with the characteristics of Inner

Mongolia's regional industries. Meanwhile, the "mentorship" mechanism is generally absent, resulting in unclear growth paths and slow development for young cadres.

Inadequate incentive mechanisms: Existing performance appraisal currently focuses on quantitative indicators such as "enrollment numbers" and "employment rates", failing to incorporate key dimensions like "team collaboration effectiveness", "innovative achievements", and "quality of school-enterprise cooperation" into the evaluation system. This makes it difficult to effectively stimulate members' enthusiasm for participation in collaboration and innovation. Additionally, professional title promotion and merit selection have low correlation with team construction effectiveness, further contributing to the tendency of "valuing personal performance over team development".

Weak team culture construction: The spirit of educators has not been effectively integrated into the process of team culture shaping. Most schools only promote it through superficial forms such as slogan publicity and conference emphasis, without translating it into specific behavioral norms and management requirements. This causes team members to lack shared value guidance and mission motivation, affecting overall cohesion and sense of responsibility.

4 Paths for Constructing Leadership Teams in Secondary Vocational Schools Under the Guidance of Educators' Spirit

4.1 Concept Remolding: Calibrating the Team's Value Orientation with Educators' Spirit

4.1.1 Conducting Thematic Learning on Educators' Spirit to Deepen Mission Cognition

Regularly invite educational experts and outstanding principals from the autonomous region to deliver special lectures on "Educators' Spirit and Vocational Education Development", in-depth interpreting its core connotations and contemporary values, and guiding team members to establish a sense of mission of "cultivating talents for the country and serving Inner Mongolia". Organize members to systematically study policy documents such as National Vocational Education Reform Implementation Plan and Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region "14th Five-Year" Vocational Education Development Plan, and conduct field visits to vocational education-developed regions such as Jiangsu and Zhejiang to learn from advanced school-running concepts and management models. Hold 1-2 "Educators' Spirit Practice Sharing Sessions" every month, where team members exchange ideas based on practical cases such as promoting school-enterprise cooperation and supporting student growth, to strengthen value recognition and sense of responsibility.

4.1.2 Establishing a Mechanism for Discussing School-Running Philosophy to Align with Industrial Needs

Organize 2 "Special Seminars on School-Running Philosophy" every semester, inviting executives and technical experts from new energy enterprises (such as Beijing New Energy Group) and modern agriculture and animal husbandry enterprises (such as Mengniu Group), as well as representatives of teachers and students from the school to participate. The seminars will

conduct in-depth discussions on topics such as "how to cultivate skilled talents meeting regional industrial needs" and "paths for aligning specialty settings with industries", ensuring that the school-running philosophy resonates with regional development. Establish an "Industrial Demand Research Group" led by school-level leaders, which will join members from academic affairs, training, enrollment and employment departments to conduct industrial research every quarter and compile an Industrial Demand Analysis Report, providing a basis for the school's specialty optimization and curriculum reform.

4.1.3 Implementing a System for Leading Cadres to Connect with Enterprises to Strengthen Practical Cognition

Implement a mechanism for leading cadres to have designated connections with enterprises, requiring each team member (including school-level leaders and middle-level cadres) to link up with 2-3 local counterpart enterprises. They should conduct on-site visits at least once a month, participate in enterprise production meetings or technical training, and gain an in-depth understanding of technical standards and talent demand. Simultaneously establish an "Enterprise Connection Log" system, where members need to record visit contents, enterprise demands and improvement measures, and report feedback at weekly meetings, promoting the effective transformation of enterprise needs into specific school-running actions such as curriculum adjustment and training enhancement.

4.2 Capacity Improvement: Building a Cultivation System Guided by Educators' Spirit

4.2.1 Conducting Hierarchical and Classified Training to Improve Capabilities Precisely

School-level leaders should focus on strategic management, policy interpretation, and industry docking capabilities. They should be organized to participate in the "Secondary Vocational School Principals' Capacity Enhancement Program" of the autonomous region and visit key enterprises inside and outside the region (such as headquarters of new energy enterprises) to learn modern enterprise management experience.

Middle-level cadres should receive differentiated training based on their positions: academic affairs directors should focus on curriculum reform and digitalization of teaching management; training directors should strengthen the construction of training bases and school-enterprise cooperation docking; enrollment and employment directors should emphasize industry analysis and employment market expansion. The training should adopt a combination mode of "online courses + offline practical operation".

For young cadres, a "Young Cadres Growth Plan" should be implemented: select backbones under 35 years old to serve as school-level assistants and participate in major school decisions; assign them to secondary vocational schools in advanced regions for 3-6 months of temporary posts to systematically learn management experience.

4.2.2 Building Practical Training Platforms to Enhance Capabilities Through Practice

Organize team members to undertake autonomous region-level vocational education reform projects (such

as the "1+X" certificate system pilot and the construction of integration of production and education demonstration bases), participating in the entire process of design, implementation and evaluation to improve their comprehensive capabilities through practical experience. Establish a "Management Talent Practice Base" in collaboration with universities such as Inner Mongolia University of Technology and Inner Mongolia Agricultural University to participate in vocational education research projects. Meanwhile, set up "Enterprise Practice Positions" in cooperation with leading enterprises like Yili Group, providing regular temporary postings to enhance industry awareness and practical capabilities.

4.2.3 Establishing a Mentor Assistance Mechanism to Give Full Play to the "Mentorship" Role

Invite retired renowned principals and vocational education experts within the autonomous region to serve as "growth mentors", providing "one-on-one" regular guidance (twice a month) covering experience inheritance, problem-solving and career development guidance. Establish a two-way assessment mechanism

for "mentors and mentees", incorporating guidance effectiveness and mentees' growth performance into the evaluation system to ensure that the "mentorship" role is implemented effectively and yields practical results.

References

1. Zhao, X. H. (2025). Exploration on the path of leading the high-quality development of regional teacher teams with the spirit of educators. *Jilin Education*, 30(3), 10-12.
2. Dong, H., & Sun, S. S. (2023). Leading the high-quality development of teacher education with the spirit of educators in the new era. *Journal of Shaanxi Normal University (Philosophy and Social Sciences Edition)*, 52(5), 37-45.
3. Wang, J., & Xu, M. T. (2025). How to shape and strengthen teachers with the spirit of educators. *Journal of Northwest Normal University (Social Sciences Edition)*, 62(3), 81-89.
4. Song, H., Yuan, P. L., & Rong, Q. (2024). Connotation and structure of teachers' professional literacy in the new era based on the spirit of educators. *Primary and Secondary School Management*, (9), 9-14.